

Tunable bidirectional electroosmotic flow for diffusion-based separation

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Abstract: We present a new concept for on-chip separation that leverages bidirectional flow, to tune the dispersion regime of molecules and particles. The system can be configured so that low diffusivity species experience a ballistic transport regime and are advected through the chamber, whereas high diffusivity species experience a diffusion dominated regime with zero average velocity and are retained in the chamber. We detail the means of achieving bidirectional electroosmotic flow using an array of alternate-current (AC) field-effect electrodes, experimentally demonstrate the separation of particles and antibodies from dyes, and present a theoretical analysis of the system, providing engineering guidelines for its design and operation.

Introduction

The ability to separate different chemical or biological species is at the core of all biochemical analysis methods, from medical diagnostics^[1], through drug discovery^[2], to proteomics and genomic sequencing^[3]. Separation methods aim to take a mixture of species and divide it into its individual components, based on differences in their physicochemical properties. Diffusivity, despite being a fundamental property of any molecule, has not been extensively used for separation purposes. This is in contrast to properties such as electrophoretic mobility, size, and chemical affinity, which gave rise to most standard separation techniques (e.g. electrophoresis^[4], chromatography^[5], membranes^[6]). Moreover, in the context of chemical analysis, diffusion is often an undesired phenomenon as it is the source of dispersion, known as band broadening in chromatography and capillary-based methods.

Two approaches that leverage diffusivity for separation have been developed in the 1980s. Giddings^[7] suggested a method, now known as the H-filter^[8], in which a sample stream and an extraction stream are forced to pass adjacent to one another through a narrow channel,

during which lateral diffusion results in mass transport of high diffusivity species from one stream to the other. The H-filter allows for continuous separation from a sample reservoir, yet allows the purification of only high diffusivity species. Another approach, wide-bore hydrodynamic chromatography^[9] subjects a mixture of species to pressure-driven flow in a capillary. As follows from Taylor-Aris analysis^[10,11], species with sufficiently high diffusivity move with the average cross-section velocity, while low diffusivity species follow individual streamlines moving at twice the average velocity at the center of the channel and at zero velocity next to the walls. As noted by Harada^[12], this large variation in the propagation of low diffusivity species results in poor fractionation, and did not receive much attention in subsequent years.

Both methods illustrate well the potential of the coupling between advection and diffusion toward separation, yet they rely solely on unidirectional flow – the only flow that can be produced using a pressure gradient across a capillary or a channel. Recently, building on the work of Stroock *et al.*^[13], we introduced a method to achieve complex flow patterns by controlling non-uniform electroosmotic flows (EOF) in a microfluidic chamber^[14,15]. In particular, EOF flow patterning allows to create bidirectional flows^[13], *i.e.* have multiple adjacent streamlines flowing in opposite directions, which is not possible using pressure actuation.

We here present a concept that achieves diffusion-based separations using bidirectional flow, which is characterized by strips of opposite velocities, with a sharp momentum gradient between them. Low diffusivity species experience little dispersion and are carried by advection (contrary to wide-bore hydrodynamic chromatography), whereas high diffusivity species are in a diffusion

dominated regime with zero average velocity and are retained close to the chamber inlet. We term this method bidirectional flow filter (BFF).

We generate the bidirectional flow by controlling an array of gate electrodes with alternate current field effect electroosmosis (AC-FEEO), and provide details for the design of such systems. This allows the velocity of the individual flow strips to be configured to produce a desired average velocity, thus controlling the transport regime of the species. Using a Taylor dispersion approach, we present a theoretical analysis of the system, validate it experimentally, and provide engineering guidelines to design separation of different species. Finally, we provide a proof-of-concept for the applicability of the method to biomolecules, and show the separation of fluorescently FITC labeled antibodies from free dye (Alexa Fluor 555).

Results and Discussion

Working principle

Figure 1 presents the principle of bidirectional flow filter. Consider a microfluidic chamber with length L , height h and width w_{ch} connected to two reservoirs and filled with an aqueous buffer, as shown in Figure 1A. Within the chamber, the liquid is subjected to a flow pattern consisting of multiple parallel strips, each with an average velocity magnitude U and width w but with alternating directions generated by an array of gate electrodes (see the next section for experimental details on generating such a flow field). Species with different diffusivities are placed in the left reservoir and are advected into the chamber by the streamlines going from left to right. The characteristic time for a species with a diffusion coefficient D to diffuse across its strip is $\tau_d = w^2/D$, during which it will be advected over a characteristic distance of

$$L_p = Uw^2/D. \quad (1)$$

The penetration length, L_p , provides a characteristic distance for the axial advection of each species, after which it would form a disperse front, experiencing a net zero velocity. High diffusivity species would diffuse across adjacent strips faster, and thus would have a lower penetration length L_p , compared to low diffusivity species, enabling their separation.

Figure 1C demonstrates this principle experimentally, showing the separation of 1 μm beads (polystyrene) from dye molecules (rhodamine B), initially mixed together in the left reservoir (inlet). The dye, having a relatively high diffusivity, quickly reaches its penetration length, after which its front remains stationary close to the inlet. However, owing to their lower diffusivity, the beads, have a penetration length longer than the length of the chamber itself and are thus advected towards the right reservoir (outlet). SI Movie S1 provides a video of this separation.

Figure 1. Operating principle of the bidirectional flow filter. (A) The device is composed of a microfluidic chamber where a bidirectional electroosmotic flow is established on a set of strips of width w having alternating velocity direction generated by an array of gate electrodes. (B) At $t = 0$, the low-diffusivity (red) and high-diffusivity particles (green) are located on a streamline leading from left to right. The smaller (green) particles, due to their higher diffusivity, rapidly transverse across strips and therefore experience a net-zero velocity. The larger (red) particles diffuse slower and maintain their advection trajectory. (C) Raw fluorescence image showing the separation of low diffusivity beads ($D = 4.1 \cdot 10^{-13} \text{ m}^2\text{s}^{-1}$) from high diffusivity rhodamine B ($D = 4.2 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2\text{s}^{-1}$). Rhodamine B rapidly diffuses across the flow strips resulting in a disperse stationary front, while beads remain on their streamlines and are continuously advected towards the right. The running buffer in the experiment is composed of 10 mM acetic acid and 1 mM NaOH (pH 3.8). A time-lapse video showing the separation is provided in SI Movie S1.

Metrics for separation quality and design guidelines

We define the purity of the separation as the ratio of area-averaged concentration of species i , to the sum of area-averaged concentrations of all species at a given axial location and at given time,

$$P(x,t) = \bar{c}_{LD}(x,t) / (\bar{c}_{LD}(x,t) + \bar{c}_{HD}(x,t)), \quad (2)$$

where the subscript LD indicates the lower diffusivity, and HD the higher diffusivity species.

Defining the Péclet number as $Pe = (Uw^2)/(D_p L) = L_p/L$, species having a penetration length longer than the length of the chamber, i.e. $Pe > 1$, are transported along the chamber mainly by advection, with half of the strips carrying the initial concentration c_i^0 into the chamber, resulting in an average concentration of

$$\bar{c}_i = c_i^0/2. \quad (3)$$

For species whose penetration length is within the channel, $Pe < 1$, this ballistic regime no longer applies, and a Taylor-Aris type analysis^[10,11] can be employed to resolve their concentration fields. Assuming that the diffusion time scale along the depth of the channel is much shorter than the diffusion time scale across a flow strip, we solve for the depth-averaged concentration profile in the channel, resulting in

$$\bar{c}_i = c_i^0 \operatorname{erfc} \left[x \left(2\sqrt{D_{eff}t} \right)^{-1} \right], \quad (4)$$

where D_{eff} is the effective diffusion coefficient, $D_{eff} = D_i (1 + Pe_w^2/3)$, and Pe_w is the lateral Péclet number, $Pe_w = Uw/D_i$. In the SI we present the governing equations of the system and a complete derivation of the Taylor-Aris analysis.

By substituting the concentration profiles (Eq. 3 and Eq. 4) into the definition of purity (Eq. 2), we construct plots of the purity as a function of the species' diffusivities, the flow velocity U , and the width of the strips w . Figure 2 shows the theoretical purity values as function of the diffusivities of two species at $t = 5$ min for typical values used in our current design - a fixed chamber length of $L = 1$ cm, with a flow velocity of $U = 40 \mu\text{ms}^{-1}$ on $w = 100 \mu\text{m}$ wide strips. The vertical and horizontal dashed lines indicate the diffusivities of various molecules of interest such as DNA (200 bp), white blood cells, proteins (67 kDa), and small dyes. The separation purity of any two species can be obtained by reading the colormap value at the intersection of any two lines. For example, a purity higher than 99% is predicted for the separation of DNA, cells or antibodies from small molecules (here represented by a dye) due to a significant difference in their diffusivities. When both species are in a Taylor-Aris regime (right side of the transition zone of Figure 2), the purity decreases nearly linearly with the difference in the species diffusivities, $\Delta D = D_{HD} - D_{LD}$. In the SI we show how the separation of a given pair of species can be improved by tuning the system parameters such as U and w . In addition, we show how the purity could be further increased by establishing a

non-symmetric flow profile wherein the flow velocity of the returning flow strips is higher than that of the outgoing flow strips.

Figure 2. Analytical results showing the purity of the

separation for a chamber length $L = 1$ cm, and as a function of the governing parameters of the system. The accuracy of the model decreases as the Péclet number approaches unity (indicated with dashed-dotted lines), which marks the transition between the ballistic and Taylor-Aris regimes. The colormap shows purity as a function of the diffusivity of the two species for a fixed time ($t = 5$ min), velocity ($U = 40 \mu\text{ms}^{-1}$) and strip width ($w = 100 \mu\text{m}$). The typical diffusion coefficients of several species (white blood cells, DNA (200 bp), IgA antibodies, protein (67 kDa) and dye) are indicated by dashed lines. The intersection points between two such lines indicate the purity of that separation.

Generating bidirectional flow

In recent work^[14], we showed that AC field effect electroosmosis (AC-FEEO), can be used to shape desired flows in a microfluidic chamber. Briefly, EOF is the flow resulting from the interaction of an external electric field with the diffuse charge in an electric double layer (EDL). At the buffer concentrations and electric fields employed in this work the resulting velocity can be well described by the Helmholtz-Smoluchowski relation^[16] $u_{EOF} = -\varepsilon_i \zeta E / \eta$, where ε_i is dielectric permittivity of the liquid, η is its shear viscosity, E is the electric field, and ζ is the potential difference across the EDL. While in traditional EOF the zeta potential is set by the native surface charge of the surface, in field-effect electroosmosis (FEEO), the zeta potential at the surface is set by applying a potential difference between a (dielectrically coated) gate electrode embedded in the surface and the bulk liquid.

Here we present a configuration of AC-FEEO for creating bidirectional flows. Figure 3A-B presents respectively an image and a schematic of the microfluidic device which is based on $L=10$ mm long, $w_{ch}=100 \mu\text{m}$ wide, and $h=15 \mu\text{m}$ deep chamber connected to two reservoirs at its far ends. The floor of the chamber contains several rows (in the presented image two rows) of gate electrodes covered by a dielectric layer. Two additional C-shaped

(uncoated) electrodes in each of the reservoirs drive the electric field through the chamber. To achieve strips of uniform flow, the zeta potential of all electrodes in a given row must be uniform. Because the bulk potential is non-uniform across the chamber, each electrode must be assigned a different absolute voltage value. Our design makes use of a single voltage source for each flow direction, with the required voltage distribution achieved through a series of on-chip resistors, as shown in Figure 3B.

Figure 4 shows an experimentally measured flow field generated by four rows of gate electrodes. These results are obtained from a time-lapse video showing the flow field which is provided in the SI Movie S2. Figure 4A shows the vector map of the flow, which is obtained using particle image velocimetry (PIV) analysis of tracer particles (fluorescent beads) placed in the chamber, overlaid on an image of the electrode structure. Figure 4B presents the line-averaged flow velocity along the y-direction, showing the opposite flow across the electrodes.

In the SI, we provide details of the fabrication, circuit design, and experimental setup. We also present an alternative method of creating bidirectional flows where the field-effect gate electrodes are replaced by chemical surface charge patterning^[15,17].

Figure 3. Generation of bidirectional electroosmotic flow using AC-FEEO. (A) Photograph of the device, and (B) illustration of the device composed of a microfluidic chamber with driving and ground electrode in the reservoir, an array of gate electrodes, a network of resistors ($R, R_{ext}^{(1)}, R_{ext}^{(2)}$) and three voltage power supplies ($V, V^{(1)}, V^{(2)}$). For simplicity, only two rows of gate electrode are shown. The network of resistors sets the potential of the gate in any of the rows such that the difference between the bulk and the gate potential is kept constant and the EOF (white arrows) is uniform. Pads are used to interface with the external resistors and the power supplies.

Figure 4. Experimental measurement of the AC-FEEO induced bidirectional flow field. (A) Vector map of the flow field generated by four rows of 100 μm wide gate electrodes, overlaid on an image of the electrode structure. The flow field is obtained by PIV^[18,19] analysis of a series of sequential frames of the video provided in the SI Movie S2 using a gate potential of $\Delta\phi = 50V$ and a driving field of 150 V/cm. (B) Line-averaged (along the horizontal, x-axis) flow velocity as a function of the y-direction, showing the inversion in flow direction across electrode rows.

Experimental validation of the penetration length scaling

Eq.1 predicts a finite penetration length for any species injected into a symmetric (zero net mass flux) bidirectional flow field. Figure 5A shows the time-evolution of Rhodamine B in a two-strip device. The dye is loaded into the left reservoir and is initially advected into the chamber by the outgoing flow as indicated in the inset showing fluorescence images of the dye at three different times. The curve shows the location of the leading edge of the concentration vs time and indicates an advective phase dominated regime for the first ~90 s, and a diffusion dominated regime at longer times. In the advective phase, the dye front fills in the chamber with an exponentially decaying velocity, corresponding to a transition from a ballistic regime to a Taylor-Aris regime with zero average velocity. Once the lateral diffusion balances the axial advection, the front essentially stops and the transport further in the chamber is due only to diffusion. Figure 5B shows the measured penetration length L_p , as a function of Uw^2/D for different flow velocities and different strip widths, showing a linear behavior, in excellent agreement with the predicted scaling.

Experimental demonstration of separation

Our current device used in the separation experiments consist of a 1 cm long chamber containing four rows of 100 μm wide gate electrodes configured to generate equal and opposite velocity magnitudes of $20 \mu\text{ms}^{-1}$. As shown in Figure 2, for these system parameters, high purity can be expected for separation of antibodies from dye molecules. As a proof of concept, here we choose to separate fluorescently labeled antibodies from free dye, demonstrating the applicability of the method to biospecies.

Figure 5. Experimental measurements of the penetration length L_p . (A) Time-evolution of the migration of rhodamine B ($D=4.2 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2\text{s}^{-1}$), noted as $I(t)$, in a chamber with an established bidirectional flow ($U = 25 \mu\text{m/s}^{-1}$, $w=100 \mu\text{m}$). The insets show the distribution of the dye in the chamber at three different times. The dye initially exhibits a front which propagates from left to right, but eventually stops and forms a disperse front in the chamber. We define the penetration length as the distance from the chamber entrance to the concentration front when the diffusion dominated regime is reached. (B) Experimental results showing the penetration length of rhodamine B as a function of the flow velocity and the width of the strip. The experiments are performed for three flow velocities (12.5 , 17.5 , $25 \mu\text{m/s}^{-1}$) and two widths of the strips ($100 \mu\text{m}$ in black, $40 \mu\text{m}$ in grey). As expected from the theory, the penetration length scales linearly with Uw^2/D (linear coefficient of 2.6), with an R^2 value of 0.98 .

To minimize the absorption of antibodies to the surface, we first flushed the devices for 5 min with a 0.25% (m/v) bovine serum albumin (BSA) in 10 mM MES and 5 mM NaOH ($\text{pH } 6$) prior to the separation. It is important to note that such coating reduces the EOF velocity by approximately 50% , and yet we obtained bidirectional flows with a velocity of $20 \mu\text{m/s}^{-1}$ using $\Delta\phi$ values of 100 V , a driving electric field of 150 V/cm , and a $\text{pH } 6$ buffer (MES 10 mM and 5 mM NaOH). As we have demonstrated before¹⁴, AC-FEEO can work well also at higher pH values, yet in this case, we refrained from higher pH buffers as those resulted in significant absorption of the antibody to the walls. Figure 6A presents the concentration distribution of both species near the left reservoir, showing that the dye has reached its penetration length, whereas the antibodies continue to be advected on the flow strip leading to the right

reservoir. Figure 6B presents the concentration of the antibodies far downstream, at a distance of $\sim 1 \text{ cm}$ from the left reservoir, in proximity to the right reservoir. Here, too, the antibodies remain on their flow strip and are advected to the right, indicating that their penetration length is greater than the length of the chamber. Figure 6C shows the average intensity profile of the species along the chamber. The penetration length of the dye is clearly visible at approximately 0.8 mm . From the intensity profile, no dye is observed to reach the outlet, thus resulting in very high purity ($> 99 \%$), as expected from the theory. The gradual loss of antibodies due to adsorption along the chamber is also visible, and approximately 85% arrive to the right reservoir.

Conclusion

The separation mechanism we demonstrated in this work is based on establishing a tunable bidirectional flow allowing a range of dispersion behaviors based on the Péclet number of different species, from a Taylor-Aris regime where species diffuse rapidly across streamlines and thus remain essentially stationary, to a 'ballistic' regime in which they follow a single streamline reaching the end of the separation chamber. We showed that the Péclet number of a given species can be controlled statically by the width of the gate electrodes, and more importantly – dynamically by changing the potential difference between the gate electrode and the bulk, thus modifying the induced EOF velocity.

In addition to its dependency on the applied potential, the EOF velocity is a strong function of the buffer properties, such as composition, pH, and ionic strength. The ideal conditions for maximizing the range of velocities are a pH value close to the point of zero charge (p.z.c) of the dielectric, and low ionic strength of the buffer. In this work, we successfully demonstrated the separation of antibodies from dye at a $\text{pH } 6$ and ionic strength of 10 mM , which are already useful conditions for biological work. However, applications to raw samples such as blood and urine remain a challenge due to their complex molecular composition, high ionic strength, and variable pH (for urine). Operation at higher pH can be enabled by a surface coating which are neutral at higher pH, or by using substrates with a naturally higher p.z.c such as Al_2O_3 ^[20]. To compensate for the reduction in EOF velocity associated with higher ionic strength, higher zeta potential values and higher driving fields are desirable. The practical limitation on having higher voltages is the threshold for the dielectric breakdown. The voltage of each gate electrode is set according to its location in the chamber and the associated bulk potential there, and the system should theoretically allow any driving voltage to be used. However, in practice, inaccuracies in the locations of the electrodes, the values of the resistors, and/or the charging time of the electrodes vs. the electrolyte, may result in potential differences larger than the designed ones, which become destructive at higher voltages. This could be potentially overcome by matching the RC time of the electrode and bulk circuits, and/or locally measuring the bulk potential at several

Figure 6. Demonstration of bio-separation in a BFF. (A – B) Fluorescent images of the separation of IgG-FITC antibodies (white, $D = 4.4 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ m}^2\text{s}^{-1}$) from Alexa flour 555 (red, $D = 4.5 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2\text{s}^{-1}$). The images are obtained by overlaying separate fluorescence images of each both species taken at the same location near (A) the left reservoir and (B) the right reservoir. The antibodies remain on the flow stirpes leading to the right reservoir, while the dye, with penetration length of 0.8 mm, quickly diffuses and remains near the left reservoir. (C) Average intensity profile of the species along the chamber. The first part of the plot corresponds to the image A and the second one to B. The experiment is performed using a physiological buffer (MES 10 mM and 5 mM NaOH, pH 6) and we use $\Delta\phi = 100\text{V}$ and a driving field of 150 V/cm resulting in flow velocity of $20 \mu\text{m s}^{-1}$.

points along the chamber for voltage feedback.

In this work we have focused on illustrating the principle of the separation mechanism, providing an experimentally validated theory for its operation, and demonstrating its applicability to biomolecules as typical targets of interest. The theory and experiments supports several analytical applications including measurement of diffusion via penetration length and detection of target-probe complex separated from a free probe background. With further engineering of the outlet to prevent outgoing streamlines from returning back into the chamber, it is also conceivable that the device could be used for preparatory application, wherein low-diffusivity species reaching the outlet reservoir are extracted for off-chip use. It is also conceivable that dynamic modification of the flow conditions would enable sequential elution of different species based on their penetration length. While many methods exist for such separations (e.g. chromatography columns, dialysis, ultrafiltration, etc.), they all require volumes on the order of microliters or larger due to dead volumes. The BFF may enable handling of sub-microliter samples, which is important for rare or expensive samples^[21] or for applications requiring low volumes such as single cell analysis^[12].

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